

A DIMENSIONAL CHANGE IN THE CULTURAL TRANSFORMATION OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR IN NEW AGE

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Introduction:

Entrepreneurism, entrepreneurship is considered to be the life blood of any economy. The entrepreneurship development has attained a significant growth with the increasing small manufacturing enterprises. The phenomenal progress during the last three decades and today it may occupy an important position in the industrial economy of India. The role of entrepreneurship in economic development involves more than just increasing per capita output and income as it involves constituting change in the structure of business and society. The study of entrepreneurship has relevance today, not only because it helps entrepreneurship better to fulfil their personal needs but because of the economic contribution of the new ventures. Entrepreneurship acts as a positive force in economic growth by serving as the bridge between innovation and the market place.

Women In Modern Areana:

The emergence of entrepreneurship in a society depends to a great extent on economic, social, religious, cultural are the psychological factors prevailing in the society. Women entrepreneurship is those who explore new paths of economic involvement and contribution. The women face identified differences such as higher interest rate, lower credit approval rates and espousal co – signature requirements that are primarily attributable to the fact that women operate younger and smaller firms that are known to meet with such financing problems.

Women Entrepreneurship in India:

The new Industrial Policy of Government of India has specially highlighted the need for special entrepreneurship programmes for women entrepreneur in the nature of product – process oriented courses to enable them to start small scale industries. It further added that the representation to women I the field of small industry development with a view to uplifting their status in the economic and social fields. A Woman Entrepreneurship movement has taken off the ground and it is felt that the moment has crossed the state of transition. It is only during the last 15 years women have started becoming entrepreneurship and started industries and business and they have yet to go a long way to be on par, par with men. A majority of Women Entrepreneurship are from the Middle Class families but have low technical education, less family responsibilities, but desire to become entrepreneurship. This potential should identified and tapped.

Segments of Women Entrepreneurship:

The segments of women entrepreneurship are classified into:

Self Help Group: Women who are well served and mentored by micro finance institutions.

Grassroots Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurship is driven by a need to augment the family's finances especially to secure their children's future – tailors, flower sellers, STD booth owners, pawn shops. With turnover aspiration of five lakh a year, they are very focussed, as they can see any increase in earnings as directly impacting their children's lives. They are hungry for formal skills and training and can clearly articulate what they want to learn that will help them earn more. Domestic family support, and better infrastructure and mechanisation is what they ask for.

Mid Rung Entrepreneur: They are driven by a need to build reputation, become known, and improve quality and satisfy creative instincts. Mostly graduate and +2, they typically have garment shops, poultry farms, export businesses etc., with turnover aspiration from Rs 50 lakh to 1 crore. Fairly well supported by the family, their biggest need is the know – how to take the quality of their business to the next level. However, they do not want to scale too much, because to them, there is an optimal level beyond which, they believe their children will get neglected.

Upper Crust: Drawn from the topmostsocial class, very well educated, with businesses like export houses, travel agencies, traders in pharmaceuticals, often adjuncts to their husband's businesses, they aspire to turnovers of more than Rs 5 crore.

Categories of Women Entrepreneurs in Practice in India:

First Category:

Established in big cities
Having higher level technical & professional qualifications
Nontraditional Items
Sound financial positions

Second Category:

Established in cities and towns
Having sufficient education
Both traditional and nontraditional items
Undertaking women services-kindergarten, crèches, beauty parlors, health clinic etc

Third Category:

Illiterate women
Financially weak
Involved in family business such as Agriculture, Horticulture, Animal Husbandry, Dairy, Fisheries, Agro Forestry, Handloom, Power loom etc.

Supportive Measures for Women's Economic Activities and Entrepreneurship:

Direct & indirect financial support
Yojna schemes and programmes
Technological training and awards
Federations and associations

Direct & Indirect Financial Support:

Nationalized banks
State finance corporation
State industrial development corporation
District industries centers
Differential rate schemes
Mahila Udyug Needhi scheme
Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI)
State Small Industrial Development Corporations (SSIDCs)

Yojna Schemes and Programme:

Nehru Rojgar Yojna
Jacamar Rojgar Yojna
TRYSEM
DWACRA

Technological Training and Awards:

Stree Shakti Package by SBI
Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India
Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD)
National Institute of Small Business Extension Training (NSIBET)
Women's University of Mumbai

Federations and Associations:

National Alliance of Young Entrepreneurs (NAYE)
India Council of Women Entrepreneurs, New Delhi
Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA)
Association of Women Entrepreneurs of Karnataka (AWEK)
World Association of Women Entrepreneurs (WAWE)
Associated Country Women of the World (ACWW)

Cultural Transformation of Women Entrepreneur in New Age Women:

In barely one generation, our culture has experienced two momentous changes in tandem. Rigid work – structures that provided relatively stability and prosperity for 150 years have given way to a more fluid post – industrial economy. Women are, for the first time, assuming positions of influences in business and public life, the confluence of these transformations has enormous indications for the future. The study of women's lives assesses the impact that social and economic revolutions are having in at least 3 realms of public life: career development and training, commercial and economic social entrepreneurship, and new physical, social and spiritual communalities that are reshaping cultures.

Career Development: Most women today are, have been, or will be part of the paid workforce. They may take 2, or 5, or even 10 years away from their jobs to raise children, to work art – time, or to volunteer for community organisation, but most eventually return to full – time work. In a rigid industrial system, where one gets an education, works for 35 years, and then retires, taking several years off is destructive to one's work –

life. But, women's traditional pattern of taking time away from work gives them an edge in adapting to the difficult, but increasingly common career transitions. Women who have chosen to make a career change after taking a few years off often re-examine the nature of their work in the light of more mature personal and professional goals. When they return to the workplace, they have a better sense of who they are, and what they want to do.

The New Market for Training: The demand for continuing education programmes among well – educated adults is growing. Although men receive most of the dollars spent on corporate training, according to the Department of Labour, women are the largest consumers of outside training, whether public seminars, college courses, or personal educational development programmes. Women more actively seek out such training opportunities. They are more willing to spend their own money and thus, take responsibility for their own training.

Cities on the Edge: The profound changes in how we live and work. Today, the massive commercial, office, and residential developments in outlying areas – dubbed edge cities by writer Joel Garreau – dominate the landscape. These communities are much more complex and self-contained than the suburbs of the 1950s, and provides a new stage for the twin revolution of gender participation, and technological and economic transformation.

The New Forms of Affiliation: Many people are approaching their current jobs as an opportunity to lay the foundation for a second or third career. People who rely for their sense of pride, enjoyment, and personal mastery on their work are not going to want to bow out at 70. One outlet for displaced employees – and women, in particular is entrepreneurship. More than one – third of all small business is now owned by women that they have a manifestation of work portfolio, encompassing many jobs that hold in lives of many lives as well as family and educational commitments.

Community and Non – Profit: Volunteer work is beginning to assume a non – professionalization character. This is evident among women who manage the home problems of a child or family – member. The result is an unparalleled growth in the minds of their people at this level to draw the same kind of commitment and energy that people devote to their voluntary activities.

The Intentional Community: The dual revolutions in social and economic behaviour are having a clear impact on individuals and organisations. As never before, people are defining their own vocations – sometimes, 2 or 3 at a time – as well as organisational affiliations. The most accomplished people see themselves as of a self – selected network; yet, as also being larger than that network. The organisations, such once – peripheral issues such as flexitime, childcare family led employee – training and development, community – service, and work – redesigned emerging as important competitive tools. That these were largely dismissed women's issues just a few years ago is indicative of the extent to which women leading today's workplace revolution.

Conclusion:

There is a great awakening among women who will produce their results by receiving an opportunity. Women excelled not only in education but also in business. Even in rural India with education, women have shown better performance. Educating women is essential for enriching personality. The need of the hour is to provide an opportunity in a conducive atmosphere free from gender differences. The non – governmental organisations have a bigger role in stimulating and nurturing the spirit of entrepreneurship among women. This emerging paradigm is also about inclusive growth through self – employment opportunities that every strata of our society can assess. This is influencing transformational change in corporate philanthropy where the “not – for – profit” charitable approach is making way for models that need to deliver self – sustaining profitability. In the end, women's greatest contribution to our changing world may be insistence on breaking the mould rather than just fitting in. This act has forced the devise new strategies and improvisations that are collectively reshaping our work.

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